

INDIA'S INDO-PACIFIC APPROACH: THE EVOLUTION, OPPORTUNITIES, AND CHALLENGES OF SAGAR

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Abstract

Global power is shifting towards Asia, and the Indo-Pacific region is emerging as the heart of geopolitical, economic and technological competition. The predominance of the West is waning, and new arenas of geopolitical competition are emerging. India, one of the key players in the region, is poised to make a strategic shift to safeguard its interests and values. From ancient times to the British era, India played a pivotal role in the Indian Ocean region. Post-independence, India faced maritime blindness due to continental threats from Pakistan and China, which eventually led to neglect of its naval potential. The paper aims to understand how India is adapting to the emerging challenges of the Indo-Pacific region. In 2015, India articulated a new maritime initiative, Security and Growth for all in the Region (SAGAR). It simultaneously integrates maritime security, economic cooperation, and regional stability, while also incorporating other foreign policy initiatives, such as 'Neighbourhood First' and 'Act East.' SAGAR aims to enhance India's status as a genuine 'preferred partner,' 'net-security provider,' an enabler of 'economic development', and the 'first responder' for humanitarian assistance and disaster relief in the region and beyond.

Keywords: Indian Ocean Region, SAGAR, Neighbourhood First, Act East, Geopolitical Shift.

I. Introduction

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India's emergence as a crucial player in the Indo-Pacific region (IPR) started well before the U.S. conception of the Asia-Pacific as the Indo-Pacific. The first modern Indian usage of the term 'Indo-Pacific' can be traced to Gurpreet Khurana's article in *Strategic Analysis*, where he argued that India and Japan, being net energy importers, must play a crucial role in safeguarding their energy security, and this can be a vital tool for cooperation between them¹. Japanese PM Shinzo Abe, during his address in the Indian Parliament, signalled the fundamental area of collaboration through the renewed importance of the 'confluence of two oceans'.² The primary articulation of the term 'Indo-Pacific' was heavily influenced by extensive energy flows, trade, and commerce passing through the region. India, being at the region's periphery, became a dominant state. However, India's influence was concentrated only in its immediate neighbourhood and the Indian Ocean region (IOR).³ The securitisation⁴ of the term began when India signalled that it would take proactive measures to secure its sea lines of communication, ensuring uninterrupted energy flows and trade. Before 2011, the term IPR was primarily used by non-governmental entities and was beginning to be incorporated into academic discourse. With Shyam Saran's article, '*Mapping the Indo-Pacific*',⁵ the term began to influence the Indian government's consciousness. The emergence of the Indo-Pacific in early 2010 has gained prominence due to India's increasing economic integration with the rest of the world, India's transformation of its financial structure into an export-driven one, and exponential growth in energy imports. Additionally, India's security

¹Gurpreet S. Khurana, 'Security of Sea Lines: Prospects for India–Japan Cooperation,' *Strategic Analysis* 31, no. 1 (2007): 139–53, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09700160701355485>.

²MOFA, 'Speech by H.E. Mr. Shinzo Abe, Prime Minister of Japan, at the Parliament of the Republic of India 'Confluence of the Two Seas,' 2007, <https://www.mofa.go.jp/region/asia-paci/pmv0708/speech-2.html>.

³Aditi Malhotra, *India in the Indo-Pacific: Understanding India's Security Orientation towards Southeast and East Asia*, 1st ed. (Verlag Barbara Budrich, 2022), <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctv2ngx5tv>.

⁴ Securitisation is a theory, principally developed by the Copenhagen School. Securitisation is the process by which a state actor frames an issue as an existential threat to its survival, which legitimises its use of extraordinary resources to deal with it. When something is labelled as a 'security issue', the debate of urgency enters in the political arena thus, making the suspension of standard procedures and taking harsh measure more acceptable to public.

⁵Shyam Sharan, 'Mapping the Indo-Pacific,' *The Indian Express* (New Delhi), October 29, 2011, <https://indianexpress.com/article/opinion/columns/mapping-the-indopacific/>.

involvement with Southeast Asia, on both sides of the Malacca Strait, prompted it to look beyond its immediate periphery. Additionally, India has strengthened its security partnerships with liberal democracies, including Australia, Japan, and the United States.⁶ India played a crucial role in shaping the Indo-Pacific after it emerged as a strategic partner following the nuclear deal, and both, India and the US were ready to accommodate each other's security concerns.

The term 'Indo-Pacific' became quite popular in the governmental arena when the Minister of External Affairs, Salman Khurshid, said, 'We are already beginning to talk about [the] Indo-Pacific'.⁷ The Indo-Pacific term has resonated with key figures at the Ministry of External Affairs, including notable individuals such as former Foreign Secretaries Shyam Saran, Kanwal Sibal, and Ranjan Mathai, as well as Secretary (East) Sanjay Singh. Notably, Prime Minister Manmohan Singh himself first adopted the term 'Indo-Pacific' in December 2012 during the India-ASEAN Commemorative Summit.⁸ Diplomatically, the term Indo-Pacific has been employed by ambassadors to the U.S., including Nirupama Rao (2011-2014) and Subrahmanyam Jaishankar (current Minister of External Affairs). Dr Jaishankar claimed that maritime claims and disputes in India's eastern neighbourhood have heightened tension in the Indo-Pacific region.⁹ It was not just diplomats who made the Indo-Pacific a common lexicon in India's strategic consciousness. Moreover, services, especially the Indian Navy, played a crucial role in propagating the idea.

⁶Manoj Joshi, *India and the Malacca Conundrum* (Observer Research Foundation, 2020), <https://www.orfonline.org/research/india-and-the-malacca-conundrum>.

⁷Minister of External Affairs, 'External Affairs Minister's speech at the 6th CUTS Anniversary Lecture on India's Economic Integration with Asia,' 2013, https://www.mea.gov.in/Speeches-Statements.htm?dtl/22153/External_Affairs_Ministers_speech_at_the_6th_CUTS_Anniversary_Lecture_on_India's_Economic_Integration_with_Asia quote.

⁸Indrani Bagchi, 'Indo-Pacific Finds Pride of Place in Asean Lexicon,' *The Times of India*, December 20, 2012, <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/india/indo-pacific-finds-pride-of-place-in-asean-lexicon/articleshow/17697636.cms>.

⁹Dr. S Jaishankar, 'Speech by Ambassador Dr. S. Jaishankar on U.S.- India Relations at the Carnegie Endowment for International Peace,' 2014, <https://www.indianembassyusa.gov.in/News?id=1998>.

Key military figures, including Chiefs of Naval Staff Arun Prakash, Suresh Mehta, Devendra Joshi, and Mihir Roy, and the former chief of the Eastern Naval Command, have actively embraced the term 'Indo-Pacific'. According to Joshi, this emerging term encapsulates the profound transformation of two vibrant regions into a singular geopolitical entity characterised by a robust maritime essence shaped by the Indian and Pacific Oceans.¹⁰ Kamal Davar, the former Chief of the Defence Intelligence Agency and Deputy Chief of the Integrated Defence Staff, has argued that, in the long run, India's core national interests extend primarily toward and beyond its eastern maritime boundaries, encompassing South East Asia and the newly emerging geographical and strategic framework known as IPR.¹¹ In the foreign policy domain, the Indo-Pacific narrative was crucial for promoting India's interests in the region. The term Indo-Pacific has gained prominence in the Indian media. The semi-official NMF serves as a platform for disseminating Indo-Pacific discourse within the think tank community. Other organisations, such as the Indian Council of World Affairs (ICWA), Aspen Institute India (AII), Indian Council for Research on International Economic Relations (ICRIER), Institute for Defence Studies and Analyses (IDSA), Institute of Peace and Conflict Studies (IPCS), and the Observer Research Foundation (ORF), also contribute to discussions related to the Indo-Pacific.

II. Evolution of India's Indo-Pacific Policy: From Narrative to Reality

India's foreign policy is fundamentally shaped by its geography, leading to prioritisation of its immediate neighbourhood under the 'Neighbourhood First' policy. This emphasis is placed on cultivating robust relationships and fostering cooperation with neighbouring countries on multiple levels, encompassing economic, political, and security aspects. The goal is to build a stable and prosperous regional environment that benefits all stakeholders. India has adopted the 'Act East' policy to complement its regional focus, aiming to deepen engagement with Southeast Asian nations and recognise the strategic

¹⁰Devendra Joshi, 'Emerging Maritime Interests in Asia Pacific an Indian Perspective,' 2013, https://galledialogue.lk/assets/template/research_papers/2013/emerging_maritime_interests_in_asia_pacific_an_indian_perspective_new.pdf.

¹¹Kamal Davar, 'Let's Not Miss the Big Picture,' Lead, *The Hindu*, September 4, 2013, <https://www.thehindu.com/opinion/lead/lets-not-miss-the-big-picture/article5093974.ece>.

and economic significance of the broader Indo-Pacific region.¹² Additionally, 'Security and Growth for All in the Region' (SAGAR) vision underscores India's commitment to promoting security and prosperity across the Indian Ocean, focusing on maritime cooperation, disaster management, and sustainable development. By actively strengthening ties with like-minded partners in the region and beyond, India aims to build a network of alliances and partnerships that can contribute to maintaining a rules-based order in the Indo-Pacific.¹³ This includes collaborating on maritime security, counter-terrorism, and trade facilitation issues. This multi-pronged strategy balances India's regional priorities with its broader aspirations in the Indo-Pacific, ultimately aimed at safeguarding its national interests and contributing to a stable and prosperous regional order.¹⁴

Nirupama Rao's definition of the Indo-Pacific as the central region connecting the Indian and Pacific Oceans, encompassing the Bay of Bengal, the Strait of Malacca, the South China Sea, the Philippine Sea, and the Western Pacific, is a geographically focused perspective. This definition emphasises maritime connectivity and strategic importance for trade, security, and geopolitical interactions.¹⁵ However, it is essential to note that 'Indo-Pacific' has broader geopolitical implications beyond its geographical definition. It has emerged as a strategic concept encompassing a wider region, including countries bordering the Indian and Pacific Oceans. This broader understanding of the Indo-Pacific reflects the region's growing interconnectedness and its increasing importance in global affairs. Therefore, it is not just the geographical nature of IPR but has evolved to encompass a more complex and multifaceted reality, reflecting the region's dynamic political, economic, and security landscape. The

¹²Sarish Sebastian et al., *India's Neighborhood Policy towards the Southeast Asian Region: A Study on Act East Policy* (CHRIST DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY, 2022),

https://india.hss.de/download/publications/A_Study_on_Act_East_Policy.pdf.

¹³Ladhu R. Choudhary, 'Assessing India's SAGAR Plan: Challenges Override Prospects,' *South Asian Voices*, December 19, 2023, <https://southasianvoices.org/assessing-indias-sagar-plan-challenges-override-prospects/>.

¹⁴Walter Ladwig, 'The Indo-Pacific in Indian Foreign Policy,' *RUSI*, May 30, 2024, <https://www.rusi.org/explore-our-research/publications/policy-briefs/indo-pacific-indian-foreign-policy>.

¹⁵Nirupama Rao, 'Nirupama Rao Defines the Future of Indo-Pacific Relations,' *GPS News*, November 22, 2019, <https://gpsnews.ucsd.edu/nirupama-rao-defines-the-future-of-indo-pacific-relations/>.

concept of the Indo-Pacific region is indeed complex and has been defined in various ways. While geographical connectivity between the Indian and Pacific Oceans takes precedence, Arun Prakash focuses on the strategic importance of the Malacca Strait as a maritime chokepoint connecting these two vast bodies of water. Combining the Indian and Pacific Oceans into a single, elongated region stretching from California to Kenya raises valid concerns about its practicality and coherence. Such a vast and diverse region would encompass a wide range of geopolitical, economic, and security interests, making it challenging to develop a unified approach to addressing the region's challenges.¹⁶ Arun Prakash's definition, while more limited in scope, provides a more manageable and strategically relevant framework for understanding the Indo-Pacific.

Source: Compilations from Observatoire de L'Indopacifique (CERI) and Thibault Fournol: Marine Regions, Flanders Marine Institute.

By focusing on the area 'on both sides of the Malacca Straits,' this definition highlights the critical role of this maritime corridor for trade, energy security, and naval power projection. The Malacca Strait is

¹⁶Sam Bateman et al., *ASEAN AND THE INDIAN OCEAN: THE KEY MARITIME LINKS*, no. 33 (S. Rajaratnam School of International Studies, 2017), <https://www.rsis.edu.sg/wp-content/uploads/2017/08/Monograph33.pdf>.

a vital link between the Indian Ocean and the Western Pacific, facilitating the flow of goods, resources, and military assets between these regions. This strategic importance has made the Malacca Strait a focal point for geopolitical competition and cooperation, with significant powers vying for influence in this crucial waterway.¹⁷ The evolving concept of the Indo-Pacific remains a subject of diverse interpretations and definitions. Another layer of complexity was added to IPR when the geopolitical triangle formed by India, Japan, and Australia, and their interconnectedness within the broader maritime systems of the Indian and Pacific Oceans, emerged. Shekhar's 'Indo-Pacific world'¹⁸ emphasises the growing strategic convergence among like-minded democracies, driven by shared concerns about maritime security, navigation freedom, and China's rise.¹⁹ This triangular framework underscores the importance of cooperation and coordination among these key players in maintaining a stable and open Indo-Pacific region.

Furthermore, there is a broader acknowledgement of the limitations of the 'Asia-Pacific' classification, which often encompasses a vast and diverse region with varying interests and priorities. By focusing on the more integrated unit of analysis represented by the India-Japan-Australia triangle, Shekhar's definition provides a more nuanced and strategically relevant framework for understanding the dynamics of the Indo-Pacific.²⁰ Multiple definitions of the Indo-Pacific reflect the dynamic and evolving nature of this vast and complex region, offering a unique perspective on its geopolitical, economic, and security landscape. By considering these diverse viewpoints, we can gain a more comprehensive understanding of the challenges and opportunities facing the Indo-Pacific and develop more effective strategies for navigating

¹⁷Dr Seyedmohammad Seyedi, 'Strategic Importance of Strait of Malacca in Southern Asia,' *ANKASAM, Ankara Center for Crisis and Policy Studies*, January 31, 2022, <https://www.ankasam.org/strategic-importance-of-strait-of-malacca-in-southern-asia/?lang=en>.

¹⁸Dr Vibhanshu Shekhar, *Rising Indonesia and Indo-Pacific World* (Indian Council of World Affairs, 2012), https://www.icwa.in/showfile.php?lang=1&level=3&ls_id=1887&lid=870.

¹⁹Cuiping Zhu, ed., *Annual Report on the Development of the Indian Ocean Region (2018): Indo-Pacific: Concept Definition and Strategic Implementation*, Research Series on the Chinese Dream and China's Development Path (Springer Singapore, 2019), <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-7693-1>.

²⁰Dr Vibhanshu Shekhar, *Rising Indonesia and Indo-Pacific World*, 2012, https://icwa.in/showfile.php?lang=1&level=3&ls_id=5171&lid=870.

this increasingly important region. Geopolitical ramifications have emerged from geographic classification.

In an official capacity, Nirupama Rao contended that ‘the term ‘Indo-Pacific’ is fast becoming a geo-strategic construct to comprehend the common opportunities, the intersecting maritime and security interests, and challenges facing India. ‘It increasingly defines the cultural, economic, political, and security continuum that straddles the Indian and the Pacific Ocean regions’.²¹ 2013 marked a significant turning point in the official recognition and adoption of the term ‘Indo-Pacific’ in geopolitical discourse. During the conference on the Indo-Pacific Region organised by the Indian Council of World Affairs, Secretary of External Affairs Sanjay Singh emphasised that the prominence of the ‘Indo-Pacific’ is increasing exponentially.²² This official acknowledgement signalled a shift in India’s strategic outlook and recognition of the interconnectedness between the Indian and Pacific Ocean regions. This growing interest in the Indo-Pacific reflected a recognition of the region’s strategic importance, its economic potential, and the need for a comprehensive approach to address the challenges and opportunities it presents. The endorsement of the Indo-Pacific paved the way for increased engagement with other regional powers, particularly the United States, Japan, and Australia. This led to the establishment of the Quadrilateral Security Dialogue (QUAD) in 2017, a strategic grouping aimed at promoting a free, open, and inclusive Indo-Pacific region. The events of 2013, therefore, marked a pivotal moment in the evolution of the Indo-Pacific concept, solidifying its position as a critical framework for understanding and shaping the region’s geopolitical landscape. This recognition has since led to increased collaboration and cooperation among regional actors as they

²¹Embassy of India, Washington DC, ‘Address by Ambassador Nirupama Rao at UC-Berkeley on 5 December 2011 ‘India and the Asia-Pacific: Expanding Engagement,’’ 2011,

<https://www.indianembassyusa.gov.in/ArchivesDetails?id=1690>.

²²Sanjay Singh, ‘Valedictory Address by Secretary (East) at the Asian Relations Conference IV: ‘Geopolitics of the Indo-Pacific Region: Asian Perspectives,’’ Address, Ministry of External Affairs, Government of India, 2013, https://mea.gov.in/Speeches-Statements.htm?dtl/21464/Valedictory_Address_by_Secretary_East_at_the_Asian_Relations_Conference_IV_Geopolitics_of_the_IndoPacific_Region_Asian_Perspectives.

seek to address common challenges and promote a stable and prosperous Indo-Pacific.²³

The National Maritime Foundation conference 2013, titled '*Geopolitics of the Indo-Pacific Region: The Next Two Decades*,' further solidified the growing prominence of the 'Indo-Pacific' concept in strategic discourse. The frequent use of the term by Naval officials highlighted the Indian Navy's recognition of the region's increasing geopolitical importance. Former Chief of Naval Staff Suresh Mehta's remarks at the NMF conference reinforced the significance of the Indo-Pacific as a critical strategic arena in the 21st century.²⁴ His assertion that the region, encompassing the Indian Ocean to the Western Pacific, rapidly surpasses the Asia-Pacific in terms of trade, investment, rivalry, competition, and cooperation, highlights the shifting geopolitical landscape and the need for a new strategic framework to address the region's complexities. The conference and the statements by high-ranking naval officials served to elevate the 'Indo-Pacific' concept to the forefront of strategic discussions, both within India and on the international stage. This increased focus on the Indo-Pacific has led to greater collaboration and coordination among regional powers as they seek to ensure a free, open, and inclusive Indo-Pacific region that benefits all stakeholders. The official recognition and widespread adoption of the term by policymakers, strategic thinkers, and military leaders have paved the way for a more comprehensive and integrated approach to addressing the challenges and opportunities in this dynamic and increasingly important region.²⁵

The emergence of the 'Indo-Pacific' concept has significantly impacted India's strategic reasoning and geopolitical outlook. India's embrace of this term stems from its explicit inclusion of the nation's name, signifying its growing importance in the region and aligning with its aspirations to be recognised as a significant global power. This linguistic shift is viewed as a strategic branding success, symbolising the rise of India in the 21st century, often referred to as the 'Indo-Pacific

²³Vivek Mishra, *India and the Rise of the Indo-Pacific*, 2013, <https://thediplomat.com/2013/09/india-and-the-rise-of-the-indo-pacific/>.

²⁴Special Correspondent, 'Focus on Maritime Interests: Ex-Navy Chief,' Visakhapatnam, *The Hindu* (New Delhi), October 9, 2012, <https://www.thehindu.com/news/cities/Visakhapatnam/Focus-on-maritime-interests-ex-Navy-chief/article12551253.ece>.

²⁵Suresh Mehta, 'Chairman's Address. Annual Maritime Power Conference.,' 2013, <http://www.maritimeindia.org/article/chairman-address-adm-ret-d-sureshmehta-chairman-nmf>.

Century.’ The previous term, ‘Asia-Pacific,’²⁶ seemed to exclude India from the strategic discourse. In contrast, ‘Indo-Pacific’ integrates the subcontinent as an integral part of the Eastern world, acknowledging India’s pivotal role in the region’s geopolitical and economic landscape.²⁷ This emphasis on India’s role in the Indo-Pacific allows the country to leverage its unique geographical position as a bridge between the Indian and Pacific Oceans,²⁸ enabling it to play a crucial role in promoting maritime security, connectivity, and economic integration.²⁹

Furthermore, the ‘Indo-Pacific’ concept resonates with India’s strategic ambitions and desire to shape the regional order. By promoting this term, India asserts its strategic autonomy and strengthens its regional partnerships, particularly with like-minded democracies such as the United States, Japan, and Australia. Arun Prakash, a former Indian naval chief, emphasises the importance of terminology in shaping perceptions and influence, arguing that the ‘Asia-Pacific’ label tends to marginalise India’s significance. At the same time, the ‘Indo-Pacific’ clearly positions India as a central and indispensable component of the region. This linguistic shift reflects India’s growing confidence, ambition, and status, providing a platform for India to contribute to shaping the regional security architecture and promote a free, open, and inclusive Indo-Pacific that benefits all stakeholders.³⁰ Therefore, India’s adoption of the ‘Indo-Pacific’ concept represents a conscious effort to enhance its visibility and influence in the region, reflecting a broader shift in India’s foreign policy towards a more proactive and assertive approach to global affairs.

The ‘Indo-Pacific’ concept seamlessly integrates with India’s long-standing geopolitical strategies, providing a comprehensive framework

²⁶Hillary Clinton, ‘America’s Pacific Century,’ *Foreign Policy*, 2011, <https://foreignpolicy.com/2011/10/11/americas-pacific-century/>.

²⁷Rao, ‘Nirupama Rao Defines the Future of Indo-Pacific Relations.’

²⁸Ian Hall, ‘Narendra Modi and the Remaking of Indian Diplomacy,’ in *From Asia-Pacific to Indo-Pacific Diplomacy in a Contested Region* (Palgrave Macmillan Singapore, 2021), https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-7007-7_7.

²⁹Timothy Doyle and Dennis Rumley, ‘The Role of India in the Indo-Pacific,’ in *The Rise and Return of the Indo-Pacific*, ed. Timothy Doyle and Dennis Rumley (Oxford University Press, 2019), <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780198739524.003.0006>.

³⁰Patrick Köllner et al., *From Asia-Pacific to Indo-Pacific: Diplomacy in a Contested Region* (2021), <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-7007-7>.

for its regional engagement.³¹ It effectively combines India's 'Look East' and 'Look South' policies, which focused on the Pacific and Indian Ocean regions, respectively, into a unified approach encompassing its 'extended neighbourhood.' The 'Look East' policy, initiated in the early 1990s, aimed to deepen India's economic and strategic ties with Southeast Asian nations. This policy increased trade, investment, and cultural exchanges and enhanced security cooperation with Association of South East Nations (ASEAN) states. Similarly, the 'Look South' approach, since the mid-1990s, sought to strengthen India's relations with its neighbours in South Asia and the IOR, especially with Sri Lanka and the Maldives. This initiative promoted regional economic integration, humanitarian assistance, disaster management, enhanced connectivity, and addressed shared security challenges.³²

The 'Indo-Pacific' concept provides a natural extension of these policies, recognising the interconnectedness of the Indian and Pacific Ocean regions and the need for a holistic approach to address the region's diverse challenges and opportunities. By encompassing both the 'Look East' and 'Look South' dimensions, the 'Indo-Pacific' framework allows India to leverage its unique geographical position and historical ties to play a more significant role in shaping regional security architecture, promoting economic integration, and fostering cultural exchange. Moreover, the 'Indo-Pacific' concept aligns with India's vision of an 'extended neighbourhood,' which extends beyond its immediate borders to encompass a broader region of strategic and economic interest.³³ This vision recognises the growing importance of the IPR for India's economic growth, energy security, and strategic interests. By active engagement, India aims to secure its sea lanes of communication, protect its financial interests, and counterbalance China's growing influence in the region.³⁴ In conclusion, the 'Indo-

³¹David Scott, 'India's 'Extended Neighborhood' Concept: Power Projection for a Rising Power,' *India Review* 8, no. 2 (2009): 107–43, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14736480902901038>.

³²Menik Wakkumbura, 'Strategizing Humanitarian Affairs: The Bilateral Relations between India and Sri Lanka Since 2009,' in *Geopolitics of India-Sri Lanka Relations*, 1st ed. (2023).

³³Axel Berkofsky and Sergio Miracola, eds., *Geopolitics by Other Means: The Indo-Pacific Reality*, First edition (ISPI, 2019).

³⁴Tayenjam Priyokumar Singh et al., 'India and QUAD in the Indo-Pacific Region: A Perspective on Maritime Security,' *Jadavpur Journal of International Relations* 28, no. 2 (2024): 148–65, <https://doi.org/10.1177/09735984251342231>.

Pacific' concept provides a comprehensive and integrated framework for India's regional engagement. By amalgamating its 'Look East' and 'Look South' policies within the context of its 'extended neighbourhood,' India is well-positioned to play a leading role in shaping the future of the IPR, promoting regional stability, and contributing to a more inclusive and prosperous regional order.

III. From Look East to Act East: Evolution of India's Indo-Pacific Approach

Although India inherited a powerful Navy and a regional security vision from the British Raj, the newly independent nation initially adopted an inward-looking approach. Over time, India developed a policy to mitigate the significant influence of naval power on the Indian Ocean.³⁵ During the 1960s, India adopted a policy of maintaining a 'peaceful periphery' in the region.³⁶ In the 1960s, the Indian Navy received only 4% of the national defence budget. However, the 1990s marked a turning point for India's naval policy in the Indian Ocean. This allocation has risen significantly, reaching 14% in the 2017-2018 financial year. This substantial increase suggests a growing focus on maritime security for India.³⁷

India's growing economic ties with East Asia led to a heightened awareness of its strategic interests in the broader IOR. This prompted India to participate in naval exercises alongside the US and ASEAN navies, thereby shaping its geopolitical outlook. The success of India's Look East Policy (launched in the early 1990s) paved the way for its evolution into the more comprehensive Act East Policy in the 21st century.³⁸ This shift reflects India's transition from non-alignment to multi-alignment, as it seeks deeper partnerships across various sectors

³⁵Walter C. Ladwig, 'Delhi's Pacific Ambition: Naval Power, 'Look East,' and India's Emerging Influence in the Asia-Pacific,' *Asian Security* 5, no. 2 (2009): 87–113, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14799850902886476>.

³⁶Aditya Vijay, *India's Trade and Maritime Policy in the Indian Ocean Region* (Centre for Public Policy Research, 2018), <https://www.cppr.in/wp-content/uploads/2018/05/India%E2%80%99s-Trade-and-Maritime-Policy-in-the-Indian-Ocean-Region.pdf>.

³⁷Laxman Behera, *INDIA'S DEFENCE BUDGET 2017-18: AN ANALYSIS* (IDSA, 2017), https://idsa.in/system/files/issuebrief/ib_india-defence-budget-2017-18_lkbehera_030217.pdf.

³⁸Shnatanu Roy Chaudhary, *From 'Look East' to 'Act East': Mapping India's Southeast Asian Engagement*, Issue Brief (Observer Research Foundation, 2025), <https://www.orfonline.org/research/from-look-east-to-act-east-mapping-india-s-southeast-asian-engagement>.

with a broader range of countries. However, regarding the expansive Indo-Pacific framework, some perceive India's engagement as primarily focused on the maritime domain, neglecting the continental aspects of the region. Although the Indian government's focus on naval power has demonstrably increased, this shift has unfolded gradually over time. It is still in its infancy compared to its regional peers. The Indian government has significantly ramped up its commitment to the Indo-Pacific region. The Ministry of External Affairs (MEA) leads the charge, establishing a dedicated department that coordinates with various regional organisations.³⁹ These include the Indian Ocean Rim Association (IORA), the ASEAN, and the Quadrilateral Security Dialogue (QUAD) grouping (including India, Japan, Australia, and the United States). While IORA and ASEAN focus on fostering regional connectivity, the QUAD represents a geo-strategic alliance. Unlike the US, which prioritises its Defence Department for Indo-Pacific affairs, India's Ministry of Defence plays a less prominent role than the MEA.

Previously, India's approach differed across sectors: the armed forces were more cautious about China, while diplomats, businesses, and politicians adopted a less guarded stance. However, the COVID-19 pandemic and the 2020 border clashes have fostered greater national unity in confronting the Chinese threat. However, there is a severe lack of a unified approach to the China challenge in the IOR. On the northern borders, Indian armed forces are maintaining a tight guard; the Indian navy is optimising its limited resources to counter the massive Chinese navy, as trade between India and China is growing at an all-time high. The major challenge is that imports are rising alarmingly, yet exports could be more active.⁴⁰

IV. Examining SAGAR in India's Indo-Pacific approach

Since Prime Minister Narendra Modi's election in 2014, India has placed significant emphasis on the Indo-Pacific region, developing a distinct and inclusive vision for its role. This vision departs from previous policies, prioritising collaboration and unity among all Indo-

³⁹Premesha Saha and Abhishek Mishra, *The Indo-Pacific Oceans Initiative: Towards a Coherent Indo-Pacific Policy for India*, Issue Brief (Observer Research Foundation, 2020), <https://www.orfonline.org/research/the-indo-pacific-oceans-initiative-towards-a-coherent-indo-pacific-policy-for-india>.

⁴⁰Pravakar Sahoo and Ashwani Bishnoi, 'Rising India-China Trade Deficit,' *Economic and Political Weekly*, September 8, 2023, <https://www.epw.in/journal/2023/36/discussion/rising-india%E2%80%93china-trade-deficit.html>.

Pacific countries. India actively engages in forums such as the Quad, while deepening its bilateral ties with Southeast Asian nations and other partners in the Indian Ocean.⁴¹ This inclusive approach aims to strike a balance between rising strategic challenges and opportunities for economic cooperation and regional stability. Central to India's vision for the Indo-Pacific is a commitment to the peaceful resolution of disputes. The region should not become an arena for competition between major powers where smaller nations are pressured to take sides. Freedom of navigation for all countries in the Indo-Pacific must be respected, ensuring no single nation dictates maritime rights. Ideally, regional challenges should be addressed through collaborative efforts within the Indo-Pacific, minimising the need for external intervention.⁴²

India emphasises adherence to established international law governing maritime traffic. This applies to all parties, regardless of the circumstances. Recognising the limitations of the previous Look East Policy, Prime Minister Modi has introduced a more proactive approach to the Act East Policy. This upgraded strategy aims to elevate India's relationships with regional partners to a new level. The Look East Policy, initiated in 1991 alongside India's economic liberalisation, was the initial step to reconnect with neglected neighbours in India's maritime vicinity. Notably, this policy yielded significant achievements and garnered bipartisan support within India's political landscape.⁴³ India's Indo-Pacific vision reflects a shift towards a more strategic and military regional outlook. The Indian Navy plays a pivotal role in this approach. It has transcended its traditional coastal defence mission to become a critical instrument for projecting New Delhi's hard power in the Indo-Pacific. This is achieved by strengthening security ties with ASEAN nations through various means, including joint patrols, bilateral

⁴¹Harsh V Pant and Shashank Mattoo, *The Rise and Rise of the 'Quad': Setting an Agenda for India*, Issue Brief (Observer Research Foundation, 2021), <https://www.orfonline.org/research/the-rise-and-rise-of-the-quad-setting-an-agenda-for-india>.

⁴²Darshana M Baruah, *India in the Indo-Pacific: New Delhi's Theater of Opportunity*, The South Asia Program (Carnegie Endowment for International Peace, 2020), <https://carnegieendowment.org/research/2020/06/india-in-the-indo-pacific-new-delhis-theater-of-opportunity?lang=en>.

⁴³Danielle Rajendram, 'India's New Asia-Pacific Strategy: Modi Acts East,' *Lowy Institute*, 2014, <https://www.lowyinstitute.org/sites/default/files/indias-new-asia-pacific-strategy-modi-acts-east.pdf>.

exercises (see Chart 2), Humanitarian Assistance and Disaster Relief (HADR) missions, and other multilateral engagements.⁴⁴

India's Indo-Pacific strategy prioritises forging closer ties with countries that share strategic interests. Interestingly, a 2017 press release following a consultation among the US, India, Japan, and Australia revealed a subtle difference in emphasis. While the US, Japan, and Australia focused on the broader Indo-Pacific concept, India highlighted its Act East Policy as the cornerstone of its regional engagement. India's Indo-Pacific strategy appears to aim at two objectives: maintaining its dominance in the Indian Ocean and leveraging valuable resources from other players to accelerate its development. To achieve this, India employs a 'Parallel Track Strategy' (also known as a Multi-Pivot Strategy or Multi-aligned Diplomacy).⁴⁵ At the second 'Indo-Pacific Regional Dialogue,' India defined its vision for the region, recognising three rising powers (China, India and Iran), two established powers (Japan and Russia), four neutral states (Indonesia, Singapore, South Korea and Vietnam), a revisionist power (North Korea), and the US as a superpower.⁴⁶ This categorisation informs India's Indo-Pacific strategy, which seeks to build constructive relationships with all key regional players. India prioritises a balanced approach, emphasising security alongside economic development and viewing them as equally important. Economic and trade growth is central to India's goals within the region. This strategy contrasts with the US approach: the US prioritises security while India balances security with economic development, and the US excludes Russia and Iran.⁴⁷ At the same time, India seeks to maintain connections, and the US advocates for

⁴⁴David Brewster, 'India's Defense Strategy and the India-ASEAN Relationship,' *India Review* 12, no. 3 (2013): 151–64, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14736489.2013.820987>.

⁴⁵Cuiping Zhu, ed., *Annual Report on the Development of the Indian Ocean Region*, 1st ed. 2019 edition (Springer Verlag, Singapore, 2019), <https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&opi=89978449&url=https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-981-13-7693-1&ved=2ahUKEwjhgM--xLeGAXvt7jgGHbw5KykQFnoECBoQAQ&usg=AOvVaw3azwYzxJrUG2xlZTAEIHTp>.

⁴⁶David Scott, 'India and the Allure of the 'Indo-Pacific,'' *International Studies* 49, nos. 3–4 (2012): 165–88, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020881714534038>.

⁴⁷Sarabjeet S Parmar, *US National Strategies of the Biden Administration: A Fragile Exercise in Shuffling Priorities* (National Maritime Foundation, 2022), <https://maritimeindia.org/us-national-strategies-of-the-biden-administration-a-fragile-exercise-in-shuffling-priorities/>.

containing China, while India favours continued economic engagement. These convergences can encompass shared regional threats and challenges, as well as complementary capabilities that mutually benefit both nations. Previously, India might not have reciprocated interest from other countries due to the absence of a comprehensive regional policy.

Although the 'extended neighbourhood policy' predates Prime Minister Modi, the 'Act East Policy' has provided a framework for actively exploring these strategic convergences. Prime Minister Modi's Act East Policy has ushered in a surge of diplomatic activity. High-level visits between India and its maritime neighbours have become significantly more frequent. Previously neglected countries are now receiving focused attention. This underscores the seriousness of India's new, proactive foreign policy approach, establishing itself as a permanent force that can provide active security in the region.

This concept encourages India to engage with countries beyond its immediate South Asian and Indian Ocean neighbours. It serves as a framework for India's outward-looking approach, encompassing the eastern, southern, northern, and western regions. Some have dubbed this a comprehensive '360-degree vision' of opportunities beyond South Asia.⁴⁸ The concept of an 'extended neighbourhood' has been a cornerstone of Indian foreign policy for some time. Defence Minister Pranab Mukherjee highlighted in 2006 that India's foreign policy takes an expanding circles approach, starting with its immediate neighbourhood and extending outwards. This outward-looking vision, a 360-degree approach, encourages engagement with countries beyond South Asia, encompassing regions to the east, south, north, and west.⁴⁹ The 'extended neighbourhood' concept rapidly gained traction within Indian foreign policy circles. Reinforcing this notion, then-Foreign Secretary Shiv Shankar Menon, during a 2007 speech in the UK, emphasised India's expanding strategic space. He stated that India's security lies in a 'neighbourhood of widening concentric circles,' extending beyond South Asia and encompassing the broader region.⁵⁰

⁴⁸Parag Khanna and Raja Mohan, 'Getting India Right,' *Policy Review*, February 1, 2006, <https://www.hoover.org/research/getting-india-right>.

⁴⁹Defence Minister of India, 'Address by Mr. Pranab Mukherjee, Defence Minister on 'India's Strategic Perspective' at Harvard University,' Harvard University, 2006, <https://www.indianembassyusa.gov.in/ArchivesDetails?id=639>.

⁵⁰Minister of External Affairs, 'Speech by Foreign Secretary Shri Shivshankar Menon on 'India and International Security' at the International Institute of

The BJP-led government under Prime Minister Atal Bihari Vajpayee introduced the 'extended neighbourhood' doctrine to Indian foreign policy. This marked a shift in focus, going beyond India's immediate neighbours for strategic engagement. The Ministry of External Affairs officially recognised this expanded approach in its 2000-2001 Annual Report. As the then External Affairs Minister stated in 2004, the government actively promoted the concept of India as a significant power with interests extending beyond its traditional sphere of influence.⁵¹ Indian strategic analyst C. Raja Mohan lauded this shift as a bolder foreign policy, 'reflecting a newfound awareness of India's strategic interests in its extended neighbourhood'.⁵² By 2004, the concept of an extended neighbourhood, encompassing regions from the Suez Canal to the South China Sea, received official endorsement. The BJP and Congress governments supported this broader strategic outlook, signifying bipartisan consensus.

V. SAGAR and the Challenges to India's Indo-Pacific Approach

India's Indo-Pacific approach integrates two key policies: 'SAGAR' and the Act East Policy. SAGAR, launched by the Modi government, focuses on fostering regional connectivity in the Indian Ocean, reflecting India's aspirations for regional leadership. While no single official document articulates SAGAR's comprehensive approach, various maritime initiatives and events are attributed to this framework. Prime Minister Narendra Modi's address at the commissioning of the Mauritius National Coast Guard Ship Barracuda in 2015 is a primary reference point.⁵³ Further elaboration is provided in two speeches by

Strategic Studies,' 2007, <https://www.mea.gov.in/Speeches-Statements.htm?dtl/1863/Speech+by+Foreign+Secretary+Shri+Shivshankar+Menon+on+India+and+International+Security+at+the+International+Institute+of+Strategic+Studies>.

⁵¹Minister of External Affairs, 'Speech by H.E. Mr. Yashwant Sinha, External Affairs Minister of India at Woodrow Wilson Centre, Washington D.C.,' 2004, <https://www.mea.gov.in/Speeches-Statements.htm?dtl/2949/Speech+by+HE+Mr+Yashwant+Sinha+External+Affairs+Minister+of+India+at+Woodrow+Wilson+Centre+Washington+DC>.

⁵²Indian Council of World Affairs, *Celebrating 75 Years of Indian Foreign Policy* (Indian Council of World Affairs, 2023), 146, <https://icwa.in/pdfs/INdia75%20Web.pdf>.

⁵³Ministry of External Affairs, 'Prime Minister's Remarks at the Commissioning of Offshore Patrol Vessel (OPV) Barracuda in Mauritius.,' (Mauritius), 2015, https://www.mea.gov.in/Speeches-Statements.htm?dtl/24912/Prime_Ministers_.

former External Affairs Minister Sushma Swaraj at the 2nd and 3rd Indian Ocean Conferences.

The Prime Minister, during the 2018 Shangri-La Dialogue, articulated the vision of SAGAR as follows:

*'Our vision for the Indian Ocean Region is rooted in advancing cooperation in our region; and, to use our capabilities for the benefit of all in our common maritime home.'*⁵⁴

While primarily focused on the IOR, Prime Minister Modi emphasised that India's SAGAR is being actively pursued in India's eastern neighbourhood through its Act East policy. The fundamental principles and objectives of the Act East Policy are to promote economic cooperation and cultural ties, as well as develop strategic relationships. SAGAR enhances India's partnership with countries in the Indo-Pacific region through continuous engagement at bilateral, regional and multilateral levels, providing improved connectivity in its broadest sense, including political, economic, cultural and people-to-people relations. The repeated use of 'our' underscores the inclusive nature of this approach, which ensures benefits of all.⁵⁵

- The first element of SAGAR is the commitment to safeguarding India's mainland, islands, and interests. This includes working towards a secure and stable IOR and assisting those affected by disasters or distress at sea.
- The second element of SAGAR is strengthening economic and security cooperation with regional partners, particularly maritime neighbours and island states. This includes assisting in the development of their maritime security capabilities and financial resilience.
- The third element emphasises that collective action and cooperation are essential for achieving peace and security in the marine region. This involves deepening mutual understanding of naval challenges and enhancing collective capabilities to

⁵⁴ Press Information Bureau, *Tecxt of the PM's Remarks on the Commissioning of Coast Ship Barracuda* (New Delhi: Prime Minister's Office, March 12, 2015).

⁵⁵Ministry of External Affairs, 'Prime Minister's Keynote Address at Shangri La Dialogue (June 01, 2018),' 2018, <https://www.mea.gov.in/Speeches-Statements.htm?dtl/29943/Prime+Ministers+Keynote+Address+at+Shangri+La+Dialogue+June+01+2018>.

address them. It also includes supporting regional mechanisms for maritime cooperation.

- The fourth element of SAGAR is to promote sustainable development for all. This encompasses fostering collaboration in various sectors, such as trade, tourism, investment, infrastructure, marine science and technology, sustainable fisheries, marine environmental protection, and the development of a Blue Economy. Additionally, it emphasises taking a leadership role in the region and advocating for more excellent global action on climate change.
- The fifth element of SAGAR acknowledges the presence of other nations with vital interests in the region. It emphasises India's engagement with these nations through dialogues, visits, exercises, capacity building, and economic partnerships. The aim is to foster trust, transparency, adherence to international maritime rules and norms, sensitivity to each other's interests, peaceful resolution of disputes, and increased naval cooperation.

During her address at the 2nd Indian Ocean Conference in Sri Lanka on August 31, 2017, former External Affairs Minister (EAM) Sushma Swaraj outlined the key principles of India's SAGAR vision.⁵⁶

- Strengthening regional security: Enhancing the ability to protect land, maritime territories, and shared interests.
- Fostering cooperation: Deepening economic and security partnerships among countries bordering the Indian Ocean.
- Promoting collective action: Working together to address natural disasters and maritime threats, such as piracy, terrorism, and the actions of non-state actors.
- Sustainable development: Promoting sustainable regional growth through increased collaboration and partnership.
- Building trust and cooperation: Engaging with countries beyond the immediate region to foster trust, uphold maritime rules and norms, and resolve disputes peacefully.

⁵⁶Minister of External Affairs, 'Address by External Affairs Minister at the 2nd Indian Ocean Conference,' 2017, <https://www.mea.gov.in/Speeches-Statements.htm?dtl/28907/address+by+external+affairs+minister+at+the+2nd+indian+ocean+conference+august+31+2017>.

In her speech at the 3rd Indian Ocean Conference in Vietnam on August 27, 2018, the EAM expanded on the topics of connectivity and infrastructure development, which are likely influenced by the location of her address. She highlighted that India's approach to implementation includes.⁵⁷

- Promoting regional connectivity: Developing projects to enhance connections between inland and coastal regions, fostering more robust economic integration.
- Expanding regional linkages: Establishing and strengthening connections between South Asia, Southeast Asia (through the Act East policy), and the Gulf region (through the Think West policy).
- Enhancing maritime security: Contributing to efforts to bolster regional maritime security.

VI. Security element of SAGAR

If the region is envisioned in concentric circles with India at the centre, India's maritime security naturally begins at its coastline. The terrorist attacks on Mumbai on November 26, 2008, tragically exposed vulnerabilities in coastal protection. However, significant improvements have been made since then to enhance coastal defence. A Coastal Surveillance Network (CSN) has been established with sensors linked to regional nodes and Joint Operation Centres (JOCs) along the coastline. This network includes 46 radar stations from the first phase and 38 in the second.⁵⁸ The data from these sensors is integrated to form a comprehensive Common Operational Picture at the Information Management and Analysis Centre (IMAC) in Gurugram, inaugurated on November 23, 2014. This information is disseminated to 51 naval and Coast Guard stations via the National Command, Control, Communication, and Intelligence Network (NC3I).⁵⁹

⁵⁷Minister of External Affairs, 'Remarks by External Affairs Minister at the 3rd Indian Ocean Conference, Vietnam,' 2018, https://www.mea.gov.in/SpeechesStatements.htm?dtl/30327/Remarks_by_External_Affairs_Minister_at_the_3rd_Indian_Ocean_Conference_Vietnam_August_27_2018.

⁵⁸Captain Himadri Das, "COASTAL SECURITY IN INDIA: TWELVE YEARS AFTER '26/11,'" *National Maritime Foundation*, December 1, 2020, <https://maritimeindia.org/coastal-security-in-india-twelve-years-after-26-11/>.

⁵⁹Himadri Das, "MARITIME DOMAIN AWARENESS IN INDIA: SHIFTING PARADIGMS," *National Maritime Foundation*, September 30,

Table 1: Assistance Provided Under Mission SAGAR.**Assistance provided under SAGAR**

Operational Unit	Date	Country & Region	Medical Aid Delivered
Kesari	December 25, 2021 - January 7, 2022	Mozambique	(i) 500 Tons of Food Aid (ii) 55 Tons of Clothing Material
Kesari	January 7 - 11, 2022	Comoros	02 Operational Readiness Facility Containers (ORFACS)
Kesari	January 14 - 15, 2022	Port Victoria, Seychelles	Escorted Seychellois Coast Guard ship PS Zoroaster from Port Victoria to Kochi
Gharial	April 29 - May 01, 2022	Colombo, Sri Lanka	760 Kg of critical lifesaving medicines
Gharial	May 03 - 05, 2022	Male, Maldives	02 Ambulances
Gharial	May 11 - 14, 2022	Port Victoria, Seychelles	03 Saluting Guns along with ammunition
Gharial	May 27 - 28, 2022	Colombo, Sri Lanka	(i) 15750 litres of kerosene (ii) 27 Tons of medical stores

Source: Ministry of External Affairs - Created with Datawrapper

Source: Ministry of External Affairs

Beyond establishing the CSN, many initiatives have been implemented to bolster maritime and coastal security. These measures include forming a National Committee, chaired by the Cabinet Secretary, implementing biometric identification for fishermen,⁶⁰ registering fishing vessels, and establishing identification systems for these vessels, as well as conducting regular exercises involving all relevant stakeholders.⁶¹ The infrastructure of India's island territories, the Andaman and Nicobar Islands in the east and the Lakshadweep Islands in the west, is undergoing significant development. The establishment of the Island Development Agency (IDA) in June 2017, with the Home Minister as Chairman, aims to create a focused and effective plan for developing these island chains.⁶² Military enhancements in the

2021, <https://maritimeindia.org/maritime-domain-awareness-in-india-shifting-paradigms/>.

⁶⁰Staff Reporter, "Kerala Scores a First, Issues Biometric ID Cards for Fishermen," Kerala, *The Hindu* (Kozhikode), August 10, 2012, <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/kerala/kerala-scores-a-first-issues-biometric-id-cards-for-fishermen/article3751448.ece>.

⁶¹Captain Himadri Das, "MARITIME SAFETY AND SECURITY IN INDIA: FISHERIES 'MCS' A KEY ENABLER," *National Maritime Foundation*, November 21, 2021, <https://maritimeindia.org/maritime-safety-and-security-in-india-fisheries-mcs-a-key-enabler/>.

⁶²PIB Delhi, "Union Home Minister chairs first meeting of Island Development Agency (IDA)," Report, 2017,

Andaman and Nicobar Islands include runway extensions at four existing airfields and the establishment of INS Kohassa, a naval air station. In the Lakshadweep Islands, developments include the construction of Minicoy Airport, the extension of the airstrip at Kavaratti, and the establishment of naval detachments at Androth and Bitra Islands.

Table 2: Exercises Conducted in IOR.

Exercises conducted in the Indian Ocean Region		
Exercise Name	Participating Navies	Focus Area
Malabar	QUAD	Combined maritime operations, anti-submarine warfare, surface warfare, and air defence exercises
SIMBEX (Singapore-India Maritime Bilateral Exercise)	India and Singapore	Naval manoeuvres, gunnery exercises, anti-submarine warfare drills
SLINEX (India-Sri Lanka Bilateral Maritime Exercise)	India and Sri Lanka	Search and rescue operations, anti-piracy measures, naval communication exercises
LAOS (Langkawi International Maritime and Aerospace Exhibition)	Multiple states	Demonstration of naval capabilities, maritime security dialogues
KONKAN (India-Indonesia Bilateral Maritime Exercise)	India and Indonesia	Surface and sub-surface warfare drills, search and rescue operations
IND-RUSS (India-Russia Bilateral Maritime Exercise)	India and Russia	Anti-submarine warfare manoeuvres, joint operational planning
JIMEX (India-Japan Maritime Exercise)	India and Japan	Anti-submarine warfare, air defence exercises, search and rescue
AUSINDEX (India-Australia Bilateral Maritime Exercise)	India and Australia	Anti-submarine warfare, maritime security cooperation, passage exercises (PASSEX)
VARUNA	India and France	Anti-submarine warfare, air defence exercises, at-sea replenishment drills
CORPAT	India and Thailand	Maritime security cooperation, anti-piracy patrols
CORPAT	India and Bangladesh	Maritime security cooperation, anti-piracy patrols
Exercise ZAYED TALWAR	India and UAE	Maritime security, joint exercises
Exercise Milan	Indo-Pacific nations	Multinational exercise focusing on humanitarian assistance, disaster relief (HADR), maritime domain awareness, and professional exchanges

Source: Press Trust of India • Created with Datawrapper

Source: Ministry of External Affairs

India is enhancing its maritime security capabilities by significantly expanding its Navy and Coast Guard. The Indian Navy, currently operating 140 warships and 235 aircraft, is projected to have 175 warships and 320 aircraft by 2027, per the Maritime Capability Perspective Plan. This includes 59 warships and submarines under construction or on order, with most being built in India. Additionally, the government has approved the procurement of 41 more ships, six

submarines, and 30 aircraft. The Indian Coast Guard, currently operating with 158 vessels and 78 aircraft, plans to expand its fleet to 200 ships and 100 aircraft by 2030 under its Long-Term Perspective Plan.⁶³ To maintain security beyond its shores, India has implemented a strategy to ensure a naval presence throughout the IOR. In May 2017, the Indian Navy launched 'Mission-Based Deployment,' which deploys 12 to 15 warships across seven critical areas of the IOR.

Additionally, a Boeing P-8I Maritime Patrol Aircraft is deployed for surveillance missions almost daily, further enhancing India's maritime domain awareness and security posture.⁶⁴ Since October 2008, the Indian Navy has maintained a consistent presence off the Horn of Africa to combat piracy. By March 2019, 70 warships had been deployed, successfully escorting 3440 ships (including 413 Indian-flagged vessels). These efforts have thwarted 44 piracy attempts and led to the apprehension of 120 pirates. Furthermore, in December 2019, INS Trikanth escorted MV Annika, an UN-affiliated merchant vessel carrying vital relief materials for the World Food Programme. INS Kolkata, operating in the Arabian Sea, successfully intercepted the pirate ship MV Ruen on March 16, 2024, following a 40-hour operation.⁶⁵ This decisive action prevented Somali pirates from further hijacking ships in the region. The MV Ruen, a merchant vessel, had been under pirate control since December 2023. This demonstrates the Indian Navy's commitment to maritime security and regional humanitarian efforts.

The Indian Navy's deployments throughout the IOR aim to address a wide range of security threats, both traditional and non-traditional. These non-traditional threats include maritime terrorism, smuggling, transnational crime, drug trafficking, illegal migration, unsustainable fishing practices, piracy, unregulated private maritime security companies, and the spread of dangerous materials. Natural disasters, oil spills, and the effects of climate change further complicate these challenges. India considers itself a 'net security provider' in the region,

⁶³ Ministry of Defence, 2025, "Indian Coast Guard celebrates its 49th Raising Day", Press Release, Feb 1, 2025.

<https://www.pib.gov.in/PressReleaseIframePage.aspx?PRID=2098736>

⁶⁴National Maritime Foundation, 'THE INDO-PACIFIC REGIONAL DIALOGUE 2023 (IPRD-2023),' 2023,

<https://pib.gov.in/pib.gov.in/Pressreleaseshare.aspx?PRID=1976790>.

⁶⁵PTI, 'ANTI-PIRACY OPERATIONS AGAINST PIRATE SHIP MV RUEN BY INDIAN NAVY,' 2024,

<https://pib.gov.in/pib.gov.in/Pressreleaseshare.aspx?PRID=2015285>.

working to protect the interests and safety of all nations in the IOR.⁶⁶ HADR operations have become a cornerstone of India's evolving Indian Ocean security strategy, with the nation actively providing aid and establishing itself as a 'first responder' in times of crisis.⁶⁷ This was exemplified by the swift response to the 2004 tsunami and the subsequent evacuation of citizens from Yemen in 2015 (Operation Rahat), as well as earlier rescue missions in Libya, Lebanon, and Somalia. In recent years, India has extended assistance to countries like the Maldives (alleviating a drinking water crisis in 2014), Bangladesh, Indonesia, Sri Lanka, Mauritius, Mozambique, Madagascar, Zimbabwe, and Malawi. This reflects India's dedication to regional stability and well-being. Notably, Indian naval and coast guard helicopters have played a crucial role in these endeavours, saving 240 lives through medical evacuations in the Maldives alone.

In line with the Prime Minister's vision of SAGAR and India's time-tested role as a first responder in the area, India launched Mission SAGAR (See Table 1), under which an Indian Naval ship Kesari was deployed to the Maldives, Mauritius, Madagascar, Comoros and Seychelles to deliver Coronavirus-related assistance.⁶⁸ This was the first time a single operation covered all countries in the region. Under Mission SAGAR, the Indian Navy (IN) responded to requests for HADR from neighbouring countries in the IOR by delivering essential materials and medical supplies via IN ships. This aid included food, medicine, clothing, ambulances, and operational readiness containers. In addition, the Committee on External Affairs also recommended, 'Given the crucial role played by multilateral fora in the fight against the pandemic, the Committee (External Affairs Committee) feel that we can overcome this threat to humanity only by building a more sustainable and resilient world through enhanced international cooperation. Hence, the Committee strongly desires that efforts by the Government should continue to combat the COVID-19 pandemic through international cooperation and also to implement the necessary reforms in the UN and

⁶⁶MEA, *MEA Annual Report 2017-18* (2018), <https://mealib.nic.in/?pdf17900?000>.

⁶⁷Special Correspondent, "India First Responder in Indian Ocean Region: Rajnath Singh - The Hindu," *The Hindu* (New Delhi), 2021, <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/disaster-relief-india-has-proved-itself-to-be-first-responder-in-indian-ocean-region-says-rajnath/article37667077.ece>.

⁶⁸PIB, 'Mission SAGAR,' 2021, <https://pib.gov.in/pib.gov.in/Pressreleaseshare.aspx?PRID=1785282>.

other international organisations for a more sustainable and resilient world, ensuring a swifter post-pandemic recovery and rehabilitation.⁶⁹

India's defence expenditure has steadily risen from 2016-17 to 2022-23, reflecting its commitment to modernising its armed forces and addressing evolving security challenges. While the Army consistently receives the most significant budget share, the Navy and Air Force have gradually increased their allocations. This indicates a growing emphasis on bolstering India's maritime and aerial capabilities in line with its strategic priorities. The Navy has experienced a notable increase in its share of defence spending, rising from 9.73% in 2016-17 to 13.59% in 2022-23.⁷⁰ With a remarkable rise, the Navy's budget increased to an all-time high of 20 per cent. (See Table 3). This reflects India's growing recognition of the importance of maritime security in the Indo-Pacific region and its ambitions for a blue-water navy. Despite the increase in the Indian Navy's budget, it still does not match other powers, such as China and the US. The increased expenditure will likely be invested in modernising the fleet, enhancing maritime surveillance capabilities, bolstering India's presence in the Indian Ocean and strengthening the collaborative efforts with other navies (see Table 2). While the Navy receives the least funding among the three branches of the Indian armed forces, its budgetary share has significantly increased since its lowest point in 1963-64. Following the 1962 border conflict with China, the Navy's allocation plummeted to 3% of the total defence expenditure. However, the recent upward trend in naval funding reflects a shift in India's security priorities, with a growing emphasis on maritime threats and the importance of safeguarding its vast coastline and strategic interests in the Indian Ocean.⁷¹

⁶⁹Committee on External Affairs, *Thirteenth Report of the Committee on External Affairs (17th Lok Sabha) on the Subject 'COVID-19 Pandemic-Global Response, India's Contribution and the Way Forward'*. (Committee on External Affairs, 2022), <http://10.246.16.187:80/handle/123456789/845704>.

⁷⁰Laxman Behera, *Examining India's Interim Defence Budget 2024- '25*, Issue Brief (Observer Research Foundation, 2024), <https://www.orfonline.org/research/examining-indias-interim-defence-budget-2024-25>.

⁷¹Laxman Behera, *High on Revenue, Low on Capital: India's Defence Budget 2023-24*, ORF Issue Brief (Observer Research Foundation, 2023), 21, https://www.orfonline.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/ORF_IssueBrief_614_Defence-Budget.pdf.

Table 3: Share of Indian Navy in the MOD Budget

Source: ⁷²

	Assistance received, Recipient countries and year.
defense Assistance	<p>Mauritius</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dornier aircraft, ALH Dhruv, refit of CGS Barracuda Ship (2015), US\$100 million Defense LOC (2022) <p>Seychelles</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dornier aircraft (2018), interceptor boat (2015), Coastal Surveillance Radar System (CSRS), National Maritime Search & Rescue Exercise, Hydrography (2016) <p>Mozambique</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Two interceptor boats and 44 SUVs (2019), four interceptor boats and other self-defence equipment (2023) <p>Sri Lanka</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 344 (2019), 308 (2021) training courses for the Sri Lankan military. <p>Maldives</p>

⁷²Ministry of Defence, *Annual Report 2022-23* (Ministry of Defence, 2023), <https://mod.gov.in/sites/default/files/AR1314.pdf>.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Landing Assault Craft (LCA), Ship CGS Huravee (2022), patrol vessel (2023) <p>Myanmar</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Kilo-class submarine (2020)
Humanitarian Assistance	<p>Seychelles</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4 tonnes of life saving medicine (2020). <p>Mozambique</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 500 MT rice to Mozambique (2021) <p>Sri Lanka</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sunayna bought relief material for floods (2016) <p>Madagascar</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> US\$2 million to the Madagascar National Office for Management of Risk and Disaster Relief (2018)
High Impact Community Development Projects (HICDPs)	<p>Mauritius</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Metro Express, and 8 MW Solar PV Farm project (2022) <p>Seychelles</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> US\$ 4.3 million assistance for buses (2016), 2.6 million dollars for construction of Magistrate courthouse (2017) <p>Sri Lanka</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Emergency Ambulance Service project (2016)
Line of Credit	<p>Mauritius</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> US\$500 million, Special Economic package and US\$353 million (2015) <p>Seychelles</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> US\$ 100 million Defense LOC (2018) <p>Mozambique</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> US\$ 250 million LoC (2019) <p>Sri Lanka</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> US\$318 million LOCs for railway rolling stocks, upgradation of railway tracks, US\$100 million for 20 container carrier wagons, 30 fuel tanks for US\$4.27 million (2017), US\$ 100 million for solar project, US\$ 82.64 million for railways (2018), US\$ 450 million for

	<p>infrastructure projects.</p> <p>Maldives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • US\$ 500 million (2022) <p>Madagascar</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • US \$80.7 million line of credit (LoC) for agriculture development (2018)
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Table 4: List of items gifted and assistance provided under the SAGAR Initiative.

VII. Survey on India's Indo-Pacific approach and SAGAR

The idea of IPR in India's strategic community was developed and sustained by the efforts of researchers and geopolitical thinkers. Much has changed since the idea's inception in the early 2000s. I surveyed researchers, academicians, and strategic thinkers to gain a deeper understanding of this concept. This survey focuses on the (SAGAR) initiative while identifying its critical challenges in realising its objectives. A targeted survey was conducted among experts in foreign policy, maritime security, and India's military strategy to gain deeper insights into the implementation and impact of SAGAR. The respondents, comprising professors from leading academic institutions and researchers from renowned think tanks like the Observer Research Foundation and the National Maritime Foundation, provided valuable perspectives on various aspects of the initiative. The survey aimed to gauge expert opinions on India's commitments under SAGAR, the perceptions of recipient countries, and the initiative's adequacy in addressing both traditional security concerns (such as China's growing influence) and non-traditional challenges (including climate change and maritime piracy). This comprehensive analysis of expert opinions, combined with a thorough examination of SAGAR's key components, aims to provide a nuanced understanding of India's evolving role in the Indo-Pacific and its challenges in realising its strategic vision.

The survey is divided into four sections. The first deals with the SAGAR initiative and its intended objectives in the IPR. The second section addresses the key areas of focus for SAGAR, including capability enhancement, India's role as a regional player, and security

against traditional and non-traditional threats. The third section discusses the implementation of strategies and the agencies of SAGAR. This section includes how effectively multiple agencies coordinate and the operationalisation challenges for the SAGAR initiative. The fourth section of the survey addresses the challenges faced by SAGAR and how India can mitigate these challenges.

Chart: Author's own Creation • Source: Survey Conducted by Author • Created with Datawrapper

VIII.: SAGAR Initiative and India's Indo-Pacific Approach

The survey results of Section One offer a comprehensive insight into the perception and impact of India's SAGAR initiative in the Indo-Pacific region. An overwhelming majority (82%) of respondents agreed or strongly agreed that SAGAR is a pivotal framework guiding India's approach, underscoring its broad acceptance and relevance in shaping India's regional policy. While there is a consensus on the importance of the SAGAR doctrine, the extent of its influence on India's overall engagement in the Indo-Pacific elicited a more diverse range of opinions. 44% of respondents believe SAGAR has had a substantial impact, with an additional 26% citing a moderate influence. This suggests SAGAR's significant role in shaping India's regional policy and actions, though not universally acknowledged.

The responses in Section One also reveal a divided yet optimistic outlook on SAGAR's contribution to creating new norms for regional cooperation. With 46% of respondents agreeing and 11% strongly agreeing, this indicates that the experts believe there is a clear sense of potential in the SAGAR initiative to shape regional dynamics. However, 26% remained neutral, indicating a need for further clarity and evidence of its impact. The presence of dissenting voices (19.5%) underscores the importance of addressing concerns and fostering a deeper understanding

of SAGAR's benefits among all regional stakeholders. The responses in section one underscore SAGAR's widespread recognition as a crucial element of India's Indo-Pacific strategy.

Section 2: Thrust Areas of SAGAR Initiative

Agree Neutral Strongly Agree Disagree

Chart: Author's Own Creation • Source: Survey Conducted by Author • Created with Datawrapper

VII.II.: Thrust Areas of the SAGAR Initiatives

Survey responses to Section 2 regarding the thrust areas of India's SAGAR initiative reveal a complex picture, with both strong support and areas of potential concern. Overall, there is a positive sentiment towards the initiative's goals of fostering regional cooperation, capability sharing, and addressing non-traditional security challenges, particularly among smaller island nations. However, a more nuanced view emerges when considering the effectiveness of SAGAR in synergising India's interests with those of its neighbours, incentivising cooperative solutions, and facilitating a shift in focus towards non-traditional security threats. While most respondents acknowledge progress in these areas, a significant minority remain unconvinced or neutral, highlighting the need for greater transparency, communication, and targeted action to address specific concerns.

The survey also reveals a divide in opinions regarding the effectiveness of India's engagement with regional partners and the adequacy of international support for achieving the goals of SAGAR. This suggests that while the initiative has garnered significant support, there is room for improvement in building consensus, clarifying objectives, and fostering deeper collaboration among stakeholders. In conclusion, the survey results suggest that the SAGAR initiative is generally perceived as a positive step towards enhancing regional security and cooperation

in the Indo-Pacific. However, the diverse range of opinions highlights the need for continued dialogue, refinement of strategies, and concrete actions to address the concerns raised by respondents and ensure the initiative's long-term success.

Section VII.III.: Implementing Strategies and Agencies of the SAGAR Initiative

The survey results offer a comprehensive perspective on India's SAGAR initiative, highlighting its perceived strengths and areas for improvement. Respondents overwhelmingly agree that SAGAR has catalysed increased engagement with regional countries across political, security, economic, and sociocultural spheres, promoting collaboration and building relationships. Additionally, there is strong support for the idea that SAGAR has successfully aligned India's interests with those of its regional counterparts, fostering cooperation and mutual benefit in both security and economic domains. The majority also believes that SAGAR policies incentivise regional stakeholders to find cooperative solutions to global challenges, contributing to a free, open, inclusive, and rule-based Indo-Pacific order. Furthermore, there is widespread recognition of the crucial role of Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) in the successful execution of SAGAR, and a predominantly positive sentiment regarding the impact of India's financial support through lines of credit on the development prospects of Indo-Pacific states. Respondents overwhelmingly agree that institutionalising a cooperative regional security framework is essential for SAGAR's success, highlighting the importance of formalising regional security cooperation.

However, the survey also reveals areas where more work is needed. There is a notable lack of consensus regarding the level of coordination and synergy among agencies responsible for implementing SAGAR, raising concerns about potential obstacles to effective execution. Additionally, while most respondents believe India's focus has shifted towards non-traditional maritime challenges, some disagree or remain neutral, highlighting the need for continued dialogue and clarification. Concerns about the adequacy of resource allocation for the Indo-Pacific Oceans Initiative (IPOI) also persist, with many respondents expressing uncertainty or disagreement regarding the sufficiency of resources dedicated to this endeavour. Finally, while PPPs are widely supported, a few respondents remain sceptical, emphasising the importance of ensuring transparency, accountability, and alignment with public interests in these partnerships. These findings underscore the need for continued evaluation, raffinement, and communication to ensure that SAGAR achieves its full potential in fostering regional cooperation, development, and security in the Indo-Pacific. The insights gained from this survey can inform policymakers and stakeholders in further strengthening and optimising the implementation of SAGAR, addressing existing concerns, and capitalising on its strengths to create a more secure, prosperous, and collaborative Indo-Pacific region.

Section 4: Major Challenges to Implement the SAGAR Vision

Agree Disagree Strongly Agree Neutral

Chart: Author's Own Creation • Source: Survey Conducted by Author • Created with Datawrapper

Section VII.IV.: Major Challenges to Implement the SAGAR Vision

The analysis of Section 4 reveals a complex and nuanced understanding of India's SAGAR initiative among respondents. There is a prevailing concern regarding China's influence in the region, with a majority (60%) believing it hurts India's pursuits. This sentiment reflects a perception of China as a potential competitor or adversary, with its investments and projects seen as undermining India's efforts to foster cooperation and security in the Indo-Pacific. Similarly, the majority (56%) also acknowledge the geopolitical rivalry between India and China as a limiting factor in effectively implementing SAGAR, highlighting the challenges posed by competing strategic interests and regional ambitions.

Furthermore, there is a strong consensus (81%) on the issue of inadequate funding and resources hindering the full realisation of SAGAR's potential. This underscores the need for increased investment in various aspects of the initiative, including maritime security, disaster management, economic development, and cultural exchange. While there is optimism regarding international support for SAGAR, with 42% believing India is receiving adequate backing, a significant majority (58%) expresses varying degrees of disagreement or neutrality. This suggests a desire for a more robust commitment from like-minded states, as well as greater transparency and awareness about the extent of international collaboration. The divergence in opinions across these questions highlights the complexity of the geopolitical landscape and the need for continued dialogue and analysis to navigate the challenges and opportunities facing India's regional ambitions.

VIII. Conclusion

With the concentration of global rivalry in the IPR, India's SAGAR policy is poised to play a vital role in the region. With the endorsement of the Indo-Pacific narrative, India has signalled its intentions to play a crucial role in the Indian and Pacific oceans. However, numerous challenges of varying magnitudes require attention. First, India needs to invest in the capacity building of smaller regional countries, mainly through transparent and equitable partnerships that prioritise sustainable development and avoid the pitfalls of debt-trap diplomacy. Second, India must leverage its strengths, such as historical and cultural ties, to foster genuine cooperation and trust with its neighbours.

Additionally, there is a strong emphasis on the need for greater transparency, collaboration, and data sharing within regional frameworks, such as the Indian Ocean Rim Association (IORA) and the

Indian Ocean Naval Symposium (IONS), as well as a focus on practical initiatives that deliver tangible benefits to all stakeholders. Third, due to China's BRI, India will face a significant challenge in safeguarding its regional interests. To achieve its intended objectives, India requires a dual approach that is assertive in specific domains and accommodating in others. India should not directly compete with China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) through alternative infrastructure projects, as this could be costly and hinder India's domestic commitments. However, the importance of soft power also highlights the need for India to build trust and goodwill among the region's people through cultural exchange, educational initiatives, and people-to-people contacts. There is also a recognition of the need for increased regional investment in economic development and military capabilities, as well as a greater emphasis on maritime security cooperation and information sharing. A more pragmatic approach might focus on managing and mitigating risks through collaboration and competition.

SAGAR can have a positive impact in certain domains through its contributions to regional cooperation, capacity building, and HADR efforts. The initiative is viewed as a platform for India to demonstrate its commitment to a free, open, and inclusive Indo-Pacific and its readiness to act as a first responder in times of crisis. The emphasis on collaborative approaches, such as joint exercises and information sharing, is crucial in building trust and strengthening regional security. However, the 'net security provider terminology' suggests that it may not be the most appropriate or desirable label for India's regional role. Additionally, there are doubts about India's capacity to fulfil the role of a net security provider due to resource constraints and the need to further develop its naval capabilities.

However, in the survey responses, there is a consensus that SAGAR has significantly enhanced India's regional diplomatic profile and influence. By engaging with regional partners on various security and developmental issues, India is seen as taking on a leadership role in the Indo-Pacific. Focusing on non-traditional security threats, such as piracy, terrorism, and climate change, is also a positive step towards addressing the evolving security landscape. However, to truly realise its potential, India will need to address the concerns raised by respondents, including clarifying its strategic objectives, strengthening its naval capabilities, and ensuring effective coordination with regional partners. Internally, India should streamline bureaucratic processes and optimise resource allocation for timely and efficient implementation. Addressing these priorities will enable India to effectively project

power, enhance security, and foster peace, stability, and prosperity in the IOR. SAGAR's successful implementation and enhancement hinge on prioritising several vital areas. A recurring theme among respondents is the need to strengthen maritime domain awareness (MDA), with a focus on regional institutions such as the IORA and the IONS. This involves promoting information-sharing mechanisms and improving communication and outreach to showcase the positive outcomes of SAGAR initiatives. This involves investing in surveillance assets, developing strategic ports and infrastructure, and building capacity in regional maritime forces. Additionally, promoting economic integration, fostering diplomatic engagement, and advancing technology and innovation in the marine domain are crucial for the initiative's success. Environmental sustainability should also be incorporated into SAGAR's framework.